

Sunda Language the Parean Dialect in Kandanghaur District, Indramayu Regency – Indonesia Based on a Dialectology Approach

Bagus Andryana Kusuma¹, Wakit Abdullah Rais², Prasetya Adi Wisnu Wibowo³

^{1,2,3}Department of Program of Linguistics Faculty of Cultural Sciences, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta 57126, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research uses one of the branches of linguistics, namely dialectology. Dialectology is the study of forms of language variation seen from a group of people. The geographical location in this study is an area where the majority of people use Javanese, but in that area, there are several villages whose people speak Sundanese. The area is located in Kandanghaur Indramayu – Indonesia. Factors underlying the variety of languages, namely the acculturation of Sundanese and Javanese. In addition, Sundanese people there can use three languages that include Indonesian, Sundanese, and Javanese. Therefore, this research will be aimed at the Sundanese Parean dialect in Kandanghaur Subdistrict located in Indramayu Regency - Indonesia. The location and language chosen to show something interesting, such as the location is the spread of Javanese society, while speakers some use Sundanese. The material used is 16 Sundanesespeaking informants who follow the age factor amounting to 6 people with 3 young people and 3 parents, while the education factor consists of 6 people from 2 elementary schools, 2 people junior high school, and high school. The formal factor uses 4 people, namely 2 formal sectors and 2 non-formal sectors. The research method uses qualitative descriptive, while the data collection method uses the Ayatrohaedi field method (1979:34) and the method of listening to libat is capable with basic techniques, notes, records, fishing, and sadap Mahsun (2015: 91-93). There are many methods of presentation of data utilizing formal and non-formal methods. The results found that there are variations in the Sundanese Parean dialect from aspects that include age, education, and work. The variation is selected and sorted based on the terrain of meaning that has been determined, namely the field of meaning of the limbs, pronouns, and greetings, the terms kinship, the house, and its parts, the time of natural circumstances, and the direction, clothing, and jewelry smell and tastes, plants and fruits, and the word question and greeting. From each field of meaning, it has been found a form of language variation from each social group, so that the Sundanese Parean dialect can be said with a language that has a form of language variation.

KEYWORDS: dialectology, dialectal variation, sundanese language, and linguistics factor.

A. INTRODUCTION

Language is a system or medium commonly used by people in communicating. Some use certain sounds and media, such as paper, wood, walls, or writing mediated on certain media. Meanwhile, Indonesia is one of the countries that have many languages. The language in question is a regional language, while the national language has only one language, namely Indonesian. Therefore, the number of regional languages in Indonesia will be chosen one of these languages to be the subject of study in this study. The language is chosen in Sundanese. This language is known for languages that have a variety of forms, such as smooth, medium, and coarse variety. In addition, Sundanese has many dialects. One such variety is the Sundanese Parean dialect located in the Kandanghaur District of Indramayu Regency of Indonesia.

The Sundanese Parean dialect was chosen because there are several reasons, namely the existence of language acculturation, Sundanese people who are triglosia, geographical location close to the Indramayu sea, and residences located in Javanese communities. Alkultarasi in the region occurs between Sundanese and Javanese which makes whether there is an influence of language variations from the intersection. Sundanese people in the Kandanghaur area tend to have more than one language ability, namely Sundanese, Javanese, and Indonesian. This makes Sundanese people able to communicate with Javanese people, even though the interlocutor uses Javanese. Then, the geographical location close to the Indramayu sea makes some Sundanese people there choose to become fishermen as their livelihood. This also tends to affect language because they will meet people who do not use languages other than Sundanese. Meanwhile, the residence of those in the Java region that makes them a minority community. Meanwhile, their residence is only in three villages, namely 1) Parean Ilir, 2) Parean Bulak, and 3) Parean Girang from 18 villages in the place.

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In addition, research is the first dialectological research conducted in the place. Therefore, related studies can not be found as long as researchers search literature. The existence of this study is expected to provide preliminary data if other studies want to do similar research. It is also expected to be able to provide perfection in providing a clear picture of the Sundanese Parean dialect located in Kandanghaur District of Indramayu Regency – Indonesia.

B. METHODS

The approach in this study uses a dialectology view. Where the approach focuses on language variations that take into account geographical factors. In addition, things to note are linguistic aspects that include phonology, morphology, and lexical. Some aspects of it are elements that often give rise to forms of language variation. Therefore, a study on dialectology seeks to describe a language from the geographical aspect and pay attention to linguistic aspects. Nadra and Renawati (2009: 1) say dialectology comes from the words dialect and logi which means the science of a dialect. That is, what is learned in dialectology only includes the discussion of dialect variations found in a group of people. Meanwhile, Francis (1983: 1) argued that dialectology is a science that studies language variations used by a small group of language speakers. Therefore, each small group will give rise to different forms of variation between groups and each other. Meanwhile, based on the group of use Nadra and Renawati (2009: 2) said there are three groups, namely 1) regional dialects. 2) social dialect, and 3) temporal dialect. In the study, this used a form of regional dialect variation that was the subject of discussion.

In connection with the above, Kridalaksana (2013:49) states that dialectology is a science that studies language variations by treating them as a complete structure. That is, the language variation is determined based on what is in the field by numbers adding or subtracting the existing language. Meanwhile, Mahsun (1995:11) argues that dialectology is the science of dialects. This opinion shows that dialectology provides descriptions related to dialects, both variations, and number variations. Meanwhile, Zulaeha (2010: 1) also said that dialectology is the study of dialects or the study of language variations. That is, language variation or dialect is a form of scientific study in dialectology. Chambers and Trudgil (1980:3) assert that dialectology is the study of dialects or dialects, while Keraf (1996:143) argues that dialectology is a science that specifically studies language variations based on local differences from all aspects. Aspects meant by Keraf include linguistic aspects, namely phonology, morphology, syntax, lexical, and semantics.

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach because the data used are in the form of words. In addition, based on the naturalist paradigm also qualitative research includes five things. Lincoln and Guba (Santosa, 2017:48) say that there are five forms of axioms that are owned by the naturalist paradigm, namely 1) the nature of reality, 2) the relationship between the researcher and the researched, 3) generalization, 4) causality and 5) the role of values. . First, the nature of this research is a language located in a certain area, so that the existing data is natural and number engineered. Second, the relationship between the researcher and the researcher is communicative because the researcher has to go to the field to collect data and the researcher becomes the data itself. Third, the generalization in this study has a general nature, so that what is known number by other people is the same as what is number by the surrounding community. Fourth, the causal relationship can be seen from the form of language variation that is influenced by geographical location. Meanwhile, the fifth is the role of values that show the form of variation in the Sundanese language, the Parean dialect.

The object of research used is the Sundanese language with the Parean dialect in Kandanghaur District, Indramayu Regency. The data is the Sundanese Parean dialect in the form of lingual units, namely words, phrases, or clauses, while the data source is the Sundanese community which includes the age, education, and occupation of the informants. In connection with that, the data collection method used is field research (Ayatrohaedi 1979:34) and the listening-engagement method with basic techniques of number taking, recording, inducement, and tapping Mahsun (2017:91-93). The listening-engagement method will use the basic techniques of number-taking, recording, and tapping, while the conversational-engagement listening method is used so that the researcher is directly involved in the conversation. This is because the data is in the informant. To obtain lingual units, such as words, phrases, or clauses, researchers must discuss directly with the informants concerned. The number-taking technique is used as a way of collecting data from interviews and the tapping technique serves to hear the speech of the informant, while the inducement technique is used so that the informant can bring up the required data properly and correctly.

Meanwhile, the informants used were 16 informants of the male and female gender. In addition, the data analysis technique method uses domain, taxonomy, and componential analysis methods. Some of these techniques are useful for numbering and providing a clear picture of the variations in the Sundanese dialect of Parean. To obtain an overview, the data analysis will be presented in the form of a componential matrix table. That way, the description of the Sundanese dialect of Parean will be seen from the form of presentation because there are certain criteria, such as phone number logical, morphological, and lexical aspects presented in it.

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C. DISCUSSION

In the results and discussion, researchers have obtained data on a Sundanese dialect of Parean from a list of questions that have been prepared in advance. The informants who became the reference consisted of 16 people from several social groups, such as age, education, and occupation. For the age aspect, they are divided into two groups, namely young and old, each consisting of 3 informants, while the education group consists of Elementary School (SD), Junior High School/Madrasah Tsanawiyah (SMP/MTS), and Senior High School/Vocational High School (SMA/SMK), each of which is 2 people. The occupational groups are divided into groups of formal and number-formal workers. Formal workers are related to agency institutions, while number-formal aspects, such as traders, fishermen, farmers, and so on are 2 people each.

Table 1. Part of Body

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Kepala	-	-	-
Leher	be'eng/beuheng/ /being/bengeng	-	gulu
Badan	-		badan/awak
Tangan	lengen/leungeun	-	-
Kaki	-	-	suku/sikil

In relation to the above, variations of the Sundanese language will be described into several fields of meaning which include parts of the body, pronoun and greetings, relatives terms, parts of a house, time, natural conditions, and directions, clothes, and jewelry, smell and taste. The following is a complete explanation of the Sundanese language variation of the Parean dialect in Kandanghaur District, Indramayu Regency - Indonesia based on linguistic factors.

In connection with the table above, several fields of meaning for limbs show that there are variations in the Sundanese dialect of the Parean dialect in the Kandanghaur District. There are five vocabularies used, namely *kepala*, *leher*, *badan*, *tangan*, and *kaki*. The glossary */kepala/* does nothing show variations in the form of phonology, morphological, or lexical aspects, while the glossary */leher/* shows that there are forms of language variations based on phonology and lexical aspects. In the phonology aspect, the */leher/* glossary has several sound variants, such as */be'eng/*, */beuheng/*, */bieng/*, and */bengeng/*. If glossary */leher/* is seen from the lexical aspect, it has a vocabulary variant, namely */gulu/*. Then, glossary */badan/* has variant words, namely */badan/* and */awak/*. Meanwhile, glossary */tangan/* shows that there are variations in language that can be seen from the phonology aspect, namely */lengen/* and */lengeun/*, while glossary */kaki/* shows variations from the lexical, namely */suku/* and */sikil/*.

Table 2. Pronoun and Greeting

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Saya	kula/kola	-	aing/kami/aku
Kamu	-	Sampean	inya
Kita	-	kami-kamian	kami/kola /kita
Kalian	-	inya-inya'an/ kabean/ rea'an	inya
Mereka	-	Sekabean/batur-batur	inya/ kabeh

The table above shows that there are variations in the Sundanese dialect of the Parean dialect in Kandanghaur District from the field of meaning of pronouns and greetings. There are five vocabularies used, namely */saya/*, */kamu/*, */kita/*, */kalian/*, and */mereka/*. In the glossary */saya/* there are variations from the phonology and lexical aspects. On the phonology aspect of variation is in the form of */kula/* and */kola/*, while in lexical terms there are */aing/*, */kami/*, and */aku/* pronoun in mentioning */saya/*. Then, the glossary */kamu/* shows the variation of the morphological aspect, namely the word */sampean/*. The word has the affix */-an/* from the root word */sampe/*, while the lexical aspect is the word */inya/*. Glossary */kita/* also has the form of language variations from the morphological aspect in the form of reduplication of the word */kami-kami'an/* while the lexical aspect has three types of words which

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include /*kami*/, /*kola*/, and /*kita*/ . Meanwhile, glossary /*kalian*/ also has the form of language variations from the morphological and lexical aspects. The morphological aspects include the reduplication of /*inyainya'an*/ and the affixation of the words /*kabean*/ and /*rea'an*/, each of which undergoes the affix /*-an*/, while glossary /*mereka*/ has two language variants from the morphology aspect which includes reduplication. /*batur-batur*/ and the affixation /*sekabean*/ of the prefix /*se-*/ and the suffix /*-an*/ . Then, the lexical aspect is the word /*inya*/ and /*kabeh*/ .

Table 3. Relatives Term

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Kakek	-	bapa ende/ bapa gede	mende/embah
Nenek	-	ma uyut/ema gede	mende/nini
Ibu	emak/ema	-	biang
Ayah	bapa/bapak	-	-
Cucu	oncu/incu	-	-

Based on the table above, the variation of a Sundanese dialect of Parean can be seen from the aspect of the field of meaning of the term kinship. The vocabulary used is five which includes /*kakek*/, /*nenek*/, /*ibu*/, /*ayah*/, and /*cucu*/ . In glossary /*kakek*/ there are language variations from morphology and lexical aspects. Morphology variations can be seen from the form of phrases, namely /*bapa ende*/ and /*bapa gede*/, while in the lexical aspect there are the words /*mende*/ and /*embah*/ . Then, the glossary /*kakek*/ shows the form of variation based on morphology and lexical aspects. The morphology aspects are the phrases /*ma uyut*/ and /*ema gede*/, while the lexical aspects include the words /*mende*/ and /*nini*/ . Then, the glossary /*ibu*/ has variations from the phonology aspect, namely /*emak*/ and /*ema*/, while the lexical aspect contains the word /*biang*/ . Meanwhile, glossary /*ayah*/ has variations from the phonology aspect, namely /*bapa*/ and /*bapak*/, while glossary /*cucu*/ has variations in glossary from phonology aspects, such as /*oncu*/ and /*incu*/ .

Table 4. Parts of House

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Rumah	ima/imah	-	-
Genting	gendeng/genteng	-	-
Dinding	-	-	tembok/dinding
Pintu	-	-	-
Lantai	-	-	tekel/buruan/lantai

In relation to the table above, the variation of Sundanese dialect of Parean can be seen in the meaning field of the parts of house. The vocabulary used is five words, namely /*rumah*/, /*genting*/, /*dinding*/, /*pintu*/, and /*lantai*/ . In the glossary /*rumah*/ there are variations from the phonology aspect, namely /*ima*/ and /*imah*/ which get the sound /*h*/ at the end of the word /*ima*/ . Then, there is glossary /*genting*/ which shows the variation of the phonology aspect, namely /*gendeng*/ and /*genteng*/ which are different in the letters /*d*/ and /*t*/ . In glossary /*dinding*/ there are variations from the lexical aspect, namely /*tembok*/ and /*dinding*/, while glossary /*pintu*/ does nothing have a form of language variation. Meanwhile, glossary /*lantai*/ has variations from the lexical aspect, namely /*tekel*/, /*buruan*/, and /*lantai*/ .

Table 5. Time, Natural Conditions, and Direction

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Kemarin	kemari/kemari	ker breto	-
Sekarang	ayeuna/ayena	-	sakiyen
Mendung	ceudem/cedem	-	mendung
Kiri	-	-	kenca/kiri/ngiwe
Kanan	nganan/kanan	-	tengen/ ketu'u

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Based on the table above, it is known the form of language variation from the field of meaning, time, natural conditions, and direction. The vocabulary used is five words from glossary */kemarkin/*, */sekarang/*, */mendung/*, */kiri/*, and */kanan/*. In the glossary */kemarkin/* there are variations from the phonology and morphology aspects. The phonology aspects that appear are the words */kermari/* and */kemari/* which give to the letters */r/* variant of the word */kemarkin/*, while the morphology aspect is seen from the variation of the phrase, namely */ker breto/*. Then, glossary */sekarang/* give a variation based on phonology and lexical aspects. The glossary phonology aspect of */sekarang/* is found in the variant forms of the words */ayeuna/* and */ayena/*. This raises the sound variant */u/* in the word */ayena/*, while the lexical aspect contains the word */sakiyen/*. Then, glossary */mendung/* has various forms of phonology and lexical aspects. Variations in the phonology aspect of glossary */mendung/* can be seen from the words */ceudem/* and */cedem/* which have the sound */u/* from the word */cedem/*, while the variations are based on lexical, namely */mendung/*. Meanwhile, glossary */kiri/* has lexical variations, namely */kenca/*, */kiri/*, and */ngiwe/*. Meanwhile, glossary */kanan/* has two variations, namely phonology and lexical aspects. The phonology aspects of glossary */kanan/* are the words */nganan/* and */kanan/*, while the lexical variations are the words */tengen/* and */ketu'ul/*.

Table 6. Clothes dan Jewelry

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Baju	-	-	baju/pakean
Celana	soal/sowal	-	Celana
Gelang	-	-	gelang/pinggel
Cincin	-	ali-ali	ali/ngerining
Anting	-	-	anting/cubang

In the table above, it is known the variation of a Sundanese dialect of Parean from the field of meaning of clothing and jewelry. The vocabulary used is 6, namely */baju/*, */celana/*, */gelang/*, */cincin/*, and */anting/*. In the glossary */baju/* there are two forms of language variation from the lexical aspect of */baju/* and */pakean/*. Then, the glossary */celana/* has language variations from phonology and lexical aspects. In the phonology aspect, there are the words */soal/* and */sowal/* which get the sound */w/* in the word */soal/*, while the lexical aspect is in the form of the word */celana/*. In glossary */gelang/* there are language variations from the lexical aspect, namely */gelang/* and */pinggel/*. Meanwhile, glossary */cincin/* has variations in phonology aspects in the form of reduplication, namely */ali-ali/*, while variations in lexical aspects are */ali/* and */ngerining/*. The last glossary */anting/* has language variations from the lexical aspect, namely */anting/* and */cubang/*.

Table 7. Smell dan Taste

Glossary	Phonology	Morphology	Lexical
Harum	sengit/seungit	-	wangi
Busuk	-	-	berek/bari/bau
Manis	-	-	-
Pahit	pait/pa'it	-	letir
Asin	-	-	-

In connection with the table above, it is known that the Sundanese dialect variation of Parean from the field of meaning of smell and taste. In glossary */harum/*, there are variations from the phonology aspects of */sengit/* and */seungit/* which add the sound */u/* to the word */sengit/* after the letter */e/*, while the lexical variation is the word */wangi/*. In the glossary */busuk/* there are language variations from the lexical aspect, namely */berek/*, */bari/*, and */bau/*. Then, in the glossary */manis/* there is no form of language variation. Meanwhile, in glossary */pahit/* it has language variations from phonology and lexical aspects. In the phonology aspect, there are the words */pait/* and */pa'it/* which are distinguished by quotations, while in the lexical aspect there is the word */letir/*. Then, the glossary */asin/* also does not have the form of language variations.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that the variation of a Sundanese dialect of Parean can be seen from the meaning field of part of body, pronoun and greetings, relatives term, parts of a house, time, natural conditions, and directions, clothes, and jewelry, and smells and taste. Some of these fields show variations in both phonology and morphology aspects in the form of

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affixation or reduplication as well as lexical. Each aspect gives rise to approximately two to three words of the Sundanese dialect of Parean in the Kec. Kandanghaur - Indonesia. The knowing infrequently, some vocabularies also do know have variations, such as the words */kepala/*, */manis/*, and */asin/*. In addition, geographic factors that influence language variation are the location of the area that is directly adjacent to the people who use Javanese, so that it influences the form of Sundanese dialect variation of Parean. This can be seen from the use of the Javanese language which is absorbed into the Sundanese language, such as the word */ibu/* which refers to it as */ema/* or */emak/*. The word */ema/* or */emak/* is a word that comes from the Javanese language. However, the Sundanese people in Parean use it to refer to */ibu/*. Thus, it can be concluded that the Sundanese dialect of Parean which is located in Kandanghaur District - Indonesia has variations based on phonology, morphology, and lexical aspects.

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